

ISic1410

I.Sicily inscription 1410

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Ustica

Place of origin (modern)

Ustica

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Lost

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI140919

1. Λουκιφέ ρ [α]

2. ἀ[πέ]θανεν [τῆ] ²sc. ἔορτῆ²

3. κυρίας Ἀ-

4. γάθης.

5.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 493027

EDCS 39101539

PHI 140919

Bibliography

Kaibel, G. 1890. Inscriptiones Graecae Siciliae et Italiae, additis graecis Galliae

Hispaniae, Britanniae, Germaniae inscriptionibus. *Inscriptiones Graecae consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae Editae. Volumen XIV.* Berlin. At 14.0592 (<https://clio.columbia.edu/catalog/6873760>)
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